

ISic3391

Opus signinum inscription of Gnaeus Modius

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

ownership

Material

mosaic

Object

pavement

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2018.06.04

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Megara Hyblaea

Place of origin (modern)

Megara Iblea

Provenance

mosaic at the entrance to room i of house 13,22 in SE quarter of Megara Hyblaea

Coordinates

37.203839, 15.181060

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Megara Hyblaea, Area archeologica di Megara Hyblaea

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letters neatly formed of small black basalt stone chips. Nu has a shorter right hand vertical; omicron is equal size to the other letters; alpha off vertical, cross-bar formed by single piece; mu formed by four equal off-vertical strokes, mid-point descending fully to the base-line.

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Γναΐου Μοδίου

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation (en)

(House of) Gnaeus Modius

Commentary

Archaeologically, the 'baths of Cnaius Modius' (so called because of this inscription at the entrance) should be dated to the first century BC (so Tréziny

2018: 274), not the third-century BC as discussed in Torelli 2007

Digital identifiers:

TM 494029

EDCS 70901044

PHI 330096

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 2007.0671

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 59.1107

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 26.1102

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1975. Koiné alfabetica fra Siracusa, Megara Iblea e Selinunte?. *Kokalos.* 21: 121-153. At 152 no.18 tav.34.3

Torelli, M. 2007. Un italico nel regno di Ierone II: Cn. Modius e il suo balneum di Megara Iblea. *Sicilia Antiqua.* 4: 99-104.

Tréziny, Henry 2018. Mégara Hyblaea. 7, La ville classique, hellénistique et romaine. *CEFR.* Rome. At 273-274

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic3391. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4358482>

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